

Synthesis of 3,3'-Dimethyl-5,5'-bibenzofuranyl

K. P. Mathai

Several bibenzofuran derivatives have been synthesised either by the action of metals on appropriate halogenobenzofurans or isolated as byproducts of other reactions^{1,2}. As a part of the studies on biphenols going on in this laboratory, it was thought of interest to ascertain the feasibility of synthesising bibenzofuranyl, starting with a suitable biphenol derivative.

4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetylbiphenyl on treatment with bromoacetic ester in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone afforded 3,3'-diacetyl-4,4'-di-(*O*-ethyl acetate)biphenyl(I). This ester on hydrolysis with EtOH-NaOH yielded the corresponding acid which on refluxing with fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride provided 3,3'-dimethyl-5,5'-bibenzofuranyl(II).

*3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-di-(*O*-ethyl acetate)biphenyl.—To 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diacetylbi-phenyl (4.4 g., 0.01*M*), dissolved in dry acetone (150 ml), bromoacetic ester (7 ml) and potassium carbonate (25 g.) were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed over a steam bath for 6 hr. The acetone was removed by distillation and the precipitate after washing with water was crystallised from benzene in white needles, m.p. 149°. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 5.9. C₂₄H₂₆O₈ requires C, 65.1; H, 5.9%).

*3,3'-Diacetyl-4,4'-di-(*O*-acetic acid)biphenyl.—The above ester (3.9 g.) was heated with 10% ethanolic NaOH (50 ml) on a water bath at 60-70°. An intense red solution obtained was acidified; the precipitated acid was purified by sodium bicarbonate treatment and crystallised from acetic acid in white needles. m.p. 259°. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 4.9. C₂₀H₁₈O₈ requires C, 62.2; H, 4.7%).

*3,3'-Dimethyl-5,5'-bibenzofuranyl.—The preceding acid (1 g.) was mixed with acetic anhydride (10 ml) and freshly fused sodium acetate (5 g.) and refluxed gently over a wire-gauze for 3 hr. It was cooled and the product separating on pouring on water was collected

* All melting points are uncorrected.

1. Toda and Nakagawa, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1961, 34, 1000.
2. Hurd and Dowbenko, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 3662.

and washed with sodium bicarbonate. It was crystallised from light petroleum in long stout needles, m.p. 73°. (Found: C, 82.0; H, 5.4. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 82.4; H, 5.3%).

The author is deeply grateful to Prof. S. M. Sethna, Head of the Chemistry Department, M. S. University of Baroda, for his keen interest in course of this work and to Dr. S. S. Lalé, of the same University, for micro-analyses. Thanks are also due to the Govt. of India for awarding a research training scholarship.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
M. S. UNIVERSITY OF BARODA,
BARODAN

Received August 30, 1965.